

SUPERPOWER V. SUPERPOWER: PRESIDENT MASOUD PEZESHKIAN, THE ISLAMIC REPUBLIC OF IRAN'S QUEST FOR POWER, AND THE FUTURE OF AMERICAN-IRANIAN RELATIONS UNDER DONALD TRUMP

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Abstract:

The history of the United States and Iran have been closely intertwined since the days of the First World War, yet for the last fifty some years, relations have severely deteriorated and become much strained. With the election of quasi-reformer Masoud Pezeshkian in mid-2024, however, there is the potential for a light thaw of relations between the United States and Iran. The re-election of Donald Trump to the U.S. presidency, however, does not correlate to a potential softening. This work aims to convincingly argue that the United States must recognise that the Iranian government will always be antithetical to America's interests in the Middle East and abroad and that renegotiating on matters of regional and international importance (e.g., the nuclear deal) is paramount to reshaping American dominance and influence, especially with the Gaza War still ongoing.

Keyword: U.S.-Iran Relations, Masoud Pezeshkian, Donald Trump, Nuclear Deal (JCPOA), Disruptive Technologies, Middle East Geopolitics, Ayatollah Khamenei, Cyber Threats

Introduction

Without question, one of the most significant threats to American internal security and American power abroad is the Islamic Republic of Iran. While perhaps not as a serious a threat as China (Bergengruen, 2023) or Russia (Reuters, 2024), Iran still rankles American policymakers, national security experts, and the U.S. government overall.

During the 2024 U.S. Presidential Election, the U.S. Intelligence Community confirmed that “Iran was responsible for the hack of Donald Trump’s presidential campaign” (News, 2024) which resulted in the leaking of “internal communications from a senior Trump campaign official and a research dossier the campaign had put together on Trump’s running mate, Ohio Sen. JD Vance ... portions of a research document about” other potential vice-presidential candidates and Vance’s vulnerabilities (Passantino & Reilly, 2024). While the exact content of this material is unknown given the U.S. news media’s decision not to publish the documents (Passantino & Reilly, 2024), this is an incredibly serious violation of American sovereignty and security which is likely to result in federal charges against specific Iranian actors (Lyngaas et al., 2024).

These are not the only instances of Iran working to harm Americans to combat American national security. Beginning in October of 2023, Iran-backed militias “launched regular drone attacks on bases housing U.S. troops in Iraq and Syria” and “attacked a U.S. base in Iraq” in July of 2024 (Robertson, 2024). Also in July of 2024, the U.S. Director of National Intelligence (DNI) Avril Haines said that “Iran is becoming increasingly aggressive in their foreign influence efforts, seeking to stoke discord and undermine confidence in our democratic institutions” also co-signing a statement with the Federal Bureau of Investigation (FBI) and Cybersecurity and Infrastructure Security Agency (CISA) that Iran “perceives this year’s elections to be particularly consequential in terms of the impact they could have on its national security interests”, making a warning about Iran’s disinformation capabilities (Steven Lee Myers et al., 2024).

These (Office of Public Affairs, 2016) and other instances of Iranian attacks against the United States (Roth, 2024) (Office of Public Affairs, 2018) notwithstanding, it should be clear that Iran poses a national security risk to the safety and security of the United States. However, while it is well documented that Iran’s cyber operations and disinformation strategies are strong areas for them to engage in, their disruptive technologies field is also incredibly sophisticated and poses a threat. With the election of President Masoud Pezeshkian and a new iteration of Donald Trump’s protectionist policies on the horizon, it is

worth exploring how Trump and Pezeshkian can likely engage with one another and also how new policies could be engineered to both counter Iranian disruptive tech and re-engage diplomatically with them.

A History of Iran's Quest for Superiority

Iran clearly desires to be an adversary on par with the United States while also being a dominant player in the Middle East and surrounding regions. In many ways, Iran is already a significant geopolitical adversary in the Middle East, helping to arm like-minded rebel groups throughout the Middle East and solidifying economic and military connections with nation-states like China and Russia (Tisdall, 2024). As such, it is understandable why Iran has focused so much on developing new technologies and remaining current on weapons development.

Perhaps no other Middle Eastern nation, save for Israel (Bamford, 2024), has been as focused on acquiring nuclear materials and gaining nuclear weapons of mass destruction.

In early 2023, the U.S. Intelligence Community released their annual threat assessment report, which covers, among many aspects of the nation's national security and intelligence policies, the current intelligence and national security perspective on Iran. While their assessment does not reflect the most recent political changes in Iran, the Community assessed that Iran would "continue to threaten U.S. interests ... entrench its influence and project power in neighboring states, and minimize threats to the regime" while improving new and emerging technology for defense and intelligence gathering purposes and work to "acquire new conventional weapon systems despite of financial constraints (Community, 2023).

Clearly, Iranian development of advanced and highly technological weaponry will be a main priority for any Iranian regime, no matter the President or leader who is in control.

However, with this, it is clear to many that Iran's strategy is changing and evolving. Having become a regional power, some experts in Iran have called Iran a global power. Sune Engel Rasmussen and Laurence Norman, both journalists with a combined decades' of experience in Middle Eastern affairs and politics, wrote just after the Iranian election that Iran's exploitation of U.S. and Western diplomatic and foreign

policy missteps has made a stronger Iran in some respects (most notably militarily), yet has made an economy that “lags far behind the growth and living standards of its Gulf Arab rivals ... lost much of the public support that brought it to power, with numerous protests prompting brutal crackdowns” (Rasmussen & Norman, 2024).

Perhaps because of this internal instability though, the Iranian regime is softening in many aspects. Kenneth M. Pollack, a former Central Intelligence Agency (CIA) analyst and member of the American Enterprise Institute and Brookings Institution think tanks, writes that, through Iran’s deals with Saudi Arabia which benefited the Kingdom more than it did the Islamic Republic and their cooperation with Dubai on infrastructure matters, Iran “seems to be adding the inducement of better relations if the Arab world will shed its U.S. dependency and accept Iranian suzerainty instead” (Pollack 2023).

This poses massive problems for the United States, as having such a committed enemy align themselves with other predominantly Islamic nations in the region could very easily, steadily erode American influence. With the Gaza War effectively continuing into Trump’s administration and being a clear strain upon U.S.-Israeli relations (Hoffman, 2024) (Glucroft, 2024), it is entirely likely that Trump’s Middle East strategy will serve to alienate longtime, dependable allies in the region.

Further navigating and dictating Iran’s stratagem into the 2020s is Masoud Pezeshkian.

A Look at Reform Under Masoud Pezeshkian

Masoud Pezeshkian is Iran’s new leader and, to some, a signal of positive efforts at bringing about a new change in Iranian and American relations. A heart surgeon by trade and active in politics since the late 1990s, Pezeshkian in the past while an elected official “criticized the government’s handling of political dissent ... strongly supported the 2015 nuclear deal, frequently speaking in its favor in parliament” and gathered popular support due to his non-elite background and from populists via “his simple Persian language and anti-corruption stance” (Dagres, 2024). With the elections taking place a month after the untimely death of right-wing President Ebrahim Raisi, Pezeshkian won 54% in a runoff vote whose turnout reflected “deep public discontent

and political apathy about the theocracy” (Nada, 2024). In some respects, it seems that Pezeshkian was able to capitalize on the populism and nationalist stances of notable right-wing, anti-American Iranian politicians while maintaining a moderately anti-government policy stance to receive some measure of public support, though by no means should Pezeshkian be seen as having been granted some public mandate.

The international reaction to Iran’s election was mixed, yet cautiously positive and optimistic for Pezeshkian in broaching relations between the West and Iran (UK, 2024) (*Can Pezeshkian Fix Iran’s Relations with the West?*, 2024). Naturally, given Pezeshkian’s election in June of 2024, some five months before the U.S. presidential election, this accounts for some of the caution.

However, some doubt Pezeshkian’s commitment to reform. In early August 2024, a few weeks after his election, Pezeshkian submitted “to parliament the names of his 19 cabinet members” many of whom were seen as being either moderate or conservative in ideology or were “associated with the suppression of dissent and the widespread arrest of journalists, intellectuals, and political critics” (*Haleh Esfandiari on Iran’s New Cabinet: A Mixed Bag*, 2024). The frustration over Pezeshkian’s selections irritated many of the more liberal and progressive supporters of Pezeshkian’s administration, with Mohammed Javad Zarif, a political aide and vice president of strategic affairs, resigning and making a public statement he “was not happy with how the composition of Pezeshkian’s Cabinet was shaping up, saying he failed to fulfill his promises to include more women, young people and ethnic groups” (*Iran’s President Proposes an Ex-Nuclear Negotiator as Foreign Minister. A Woman Is Also on the List*, 2024). CBS News, having interviewed numerous academics and advocates from Iran, concluded that Pezeshkian “has no grand vision to reshape Iran’s authoritarian theocracy, or to challenge the supremacy of Ayatollah Ali Khamenei [and instead will] try to soften some of the regime’s harsher measures” (Palmer & Seyed Bathaei, 2024).

Others do not doubt Pezeshkian’s commitment to reform, but rather the practical achievements he will be able to make in Iranian politics and society. Mohammad Ayatollah Tabaar, a professor of international affairs at Texas A&M and the author of a work on the Islamic politics of Iran, writes in *Foreign Affairs* that while Pezeshkian “may gradually

attempt a bigger break from his predecessor [and] enact some new policies” he and his reformist party will largely be constrained by Supreme Leader Khamenei and the Iranian Revolutionary Guard Corps (IRGC) who look upon thawing relations with the West and any real reforms skeptically (Tabaar, 2024).

How the U.S. Can Broach Iran

The first step, it should be clear, is that dealing with Iran militarily is not an effective option or strategy. With the latest iteration of the Israel-Palestine conflict and the desire on the both the American political left and right to use a strong hand to resolve disputes with Iran, Melvin Goodman, a professor of government at Johns Hopkins and a former CIA officer, finds that such continued action “will create greater instability in the entire region; contribute to the diplomatic and political influence of Russia and China; and create a wider zone of conflict and crisis” (Goodman, 2024). Historically, American relations with Iran have a significant gap between them with hardly “any American officials who have served in Iran since essentially 1979” with no American presidential administration being “able to figure out how best to manage the challenge that Tehran poses for stability and American interests in the Middle East” (*Why Washington Has Struggled to Find the Right Policy Formula for Iran*, 2024) (Esfandiary, 2020).

Instead, in contrast with the vast majority of the past almost half century, Goodman stresses a return to diplomacy. With this, there are numerous potential avenues on how the U.S. can better engage with Iran. Internally, the United States must first understand “what it wants from Iran and the region” while also understanding that “Iran is a threat that can be managed, but not eradicated [nor] forcibly prevent Iran from seeking a nuclear weapon or running militias in the region” (Esfandiary, 2020). Any attempts to try and do the opposite would be met with only increased tensions and a further widening gap between nation-states while continuing to heighten divisions and foster Iranian geopolitical superiority with a decrease in American influence.

By taking advantage of Iran’s weaknesses, however, there is greater potential now than ever for a better relationship. Philip H. Gordon, a veteran foreign policy theorist and former National Security Advisor to Vice President Kamala Harris, argues that, given Trump’s willingness

for a potential deal, Pezeshkian's election, and the changing of Middle Eastern affairs due to the Gaza War makes concessions like "strict caps on levels of nuclear enrichment, conditions without expiration dates, limits on ballistic missiles ... even limits on Iranian regional interference" more realistic (Gordon, 2025). He further reasons that, barring Iran's limits or an overreach by the Trump administration, a deal which includes granting Iran access to "an international fuel bank" would allow Iran to claim to have preserved its right to benefit from civil nuclear-energy production and also permit Trump and the Israeli government to say that they denied Iran control over enrichment" simultaneously preventing Iran from gaining nuclear weapons and weaken their regional influence and gaining Trump the ability to "gloat about getting a 'better deal' than Obama" (Gordon, 2025).

As such, it is imperative that the United States go back and rework the contentious Iran nuclear deal. Amidst much misinformation (to include disinformation) and political polarization of the deal's inner workings, the 2015 Joint Comprehensive Plan of Action (JCPOA);

"imposed restraints on Iran's nuclear program in exchange for relief from most U.S. and UN Security Council economic sanctions ... restricted Iran's enrichment and heavy water reactor programs and provided for enhanced [International Atomic Energy Agency] monitoring to detect Iranian efforts to produce nuclear weapons using either declared or covert facilities ... [and] indefinitely prohibited Iranian 'activities which could contribute to the design and development of a nuclear explosive device' [to include research activities]" (Thomas, 2024).

When Trump entered office in 2017 and backed out of the deal, Iran "resumed enriching uranium to higher and higher levels" continuing to enrich more and more material following Israeli assassinations and attacks (Azodi, 2023). Again, while Pezeshkian has expressed a desire to rework the nuclear deal, much of this will be dependent upon the desires of Ayatollah Khamenei who, along with the rest of the Iranian government, is aware that "any easing of sanctions will first have to be negotiated with Washington" (English, 2024).

Mohammad Tabaar recommends the United States "make a good-faith effort to craft such an agreement", keep open communication channels to the Iranian government and avoid not only any initial forays with Iran

as a breakthrough but also avoid indicating “that the United States is trying to strengthen Iran’s moderates vis-à-vis its hard-right elites” (Tabaar, 2024). Ariel Levite, a Senior Fellow with the Carnegie Endowment for International Peace’s Nuclear Policy Program, similarly to Gordon, argues against reintroducing the JCPOA rather “opt for agreement on a set of principles of conduct” modeled off the 2013 Joint Plan of Action which had demonstrable success in normalizing U.S.-Iran relations and “halted Iran’s nuclear progress” (*Prioritizing Nuclear Negotiations with Iran*, 2025). Levite stresses too that the United States should “insist on comprehensively capping all Iranian nuclear weapons capabilities and activities well beyond uranium enrichment, including those not effectively covered or implemented in previous agreements” keeping in line with the fact that Iran will always have some form of nuclear program while also develop a “different approach to monitoring Iranian compliance that deprives” Iran leverage over nuclear inspectors (*Prioritizing Nuclear Negotiations with Iran*, 2025).

However, most of these policy options truly depend upon a single individual; Donald Trump. Given past experiences, Trump’s foreign policy on any given region, nation-state, or in a particular area is immensely difficult to narrow down as his behavior is quite emotional and he would be frequently prone to alternating between a nationalist and internationalist foreign policy (Castillo et al., 2024). Already, the world is witnessing a disruption that, while promised, has left journalists, academics, and observers stunned and, in the informed eyes of many, will not “produce the bonanza [Trump] predicts” (*How Emotional Reactions Shape Foreign Policy Decision-Making.*, 2024).

In Trump’s second administration, it is entirely likely the world will see similar actions to his first. Already, Trump has stated that the U.S. must exert “maximum pressure” on the Iranian government while denying “all paths to a nuclear weapon” along with limiting Iranian conventional and ballistic weaponry (*Trump Ramps up Pressure on Iran | Arms Control Association*, 2015). This is highly concerning and indicative of a continuation and escalation of Trump’s previous policies (*Trump’s Failing Iran Policy | Arms Control Association*, 2019). Yet the foreign policy on Iran will not only be dependent upon Donald Trump’s desires, but also those of his inner circle who are a concerning mix of “staunch isolationists and stalwart war hawks” (SARISOHN, 2025). This will

pose problems in crafting any Iran policy that is intent on stabilizing relations in the nation and region.

Daniel Byman, a senior fellow with the Center for Strategic and International Studies and a former employee of both The RAND Corporation and Brookings Institution, wrote that Trump “opposes negotiations and favors economic pressure in particular” yet “may be less likely to provide military support to U.S. Arab allies against Iran” and theorizes that by Trump embracing Russia it “would in turn decrease Moscow’s incentives to work with Tehran” (Byman & Trauger, 2024). With an already tense relationship between Iran and Russia at risk (*Iran’s Eastward Turn to Russia and China*, n.d.), it appears that Trump’s re-embrace of Russia, while a negative for Ukraine and Europe, could be a positive in countering Iran.

In short, a stabilization of U.S. and Iran relations is unlikely and dependent upon a known wild card (when it comes to foreign policy) acting rationally and a political insecure authoritarian nation-state shedding half a century of conservative nationalist policies to be willing to concede ground while seemingly gaining little in the immediate. The outlook for there to be a positive resolution to this decades long made breakdown in foreign policy thawing and diplomatic overture is not strong.

Conclusion

The potential for crafting a strong, effective, and mutually beneficial relationship between Iran and the United States is small. Iran, since its creation in 1979 and stemming from historical events which are no distant memory for the Iranian people (*Why the U.S. and Iran Hate Each Other*, 2022), is a nation which has a commitment to the destruction of the United States and, with any nation state that sees another as an enemy, there will be little conciliatory, productive policies to be gained. However, as with any foreign policy, it is important to remain and always continue for such placating efforts. Iranian and U.S. relations should be no different. The fact that Donald Trump is now the President of the United States makes for an enormously smaller potential at developing positive relations between nations.

However, an effort must still be made. At this point in time, the Middle East is in a crisis. Tensions between Israel and the rest of the Arab world

is increasing at a serious pace and Trump's public statements on Iran are antagonistic and will needlessly incite already strained tensions. In order for diplomatic relations to resume and continue gainfully, in order for a moderately easy coexistence to be granted between the United States and the Iranian governments, both sides must be able to see the other individual not as a mortal enemy waged in an eternal death struggle, rather simply as two nation-states both with their own sovereignty and goals.

While Iran and the United States will not become geopolitically friendly anytime soon, there is the potential for a diplomatic relationship, one which will allow the United States to claim some achievements in making the Middle East more peaceable while the Iranian government would be able to continue their own programs and maintain their own geopolitical goals. An understanding of Iran's wants and needs would put the United States in a better position with which to negotiate and, by understanding the realities of the Middle East and Iran's politics, allow them to dictate the situation going forward in the Middle East.

Reference:

- Bergengruen, V. (2023, March 8). *China's Ambitions, Russia's Nukes and TikTok: Spy Chiefs Talk Biggest U.S. Security Threats*. Time. <https://time.com/6261094/china-russia-tiktok-top-threats-to-us/>.
- Reuters. (2024, March 11). U.S. faces "increasingly fragile world order" amid Russia and China threat. *The Guardian*. <https://www.theguardian.com/us-news/2024/mar/11/us-intelligence-china-russia>.
- News, P. (2024, August 19). *U.S. intelligence officials say Iran was behind Trump presidential campaign hack*. PBS News. <https://www.pbs.org/newshour/world/u-s-intelligence-officials-say-iran-was-behind-trump-presidential-campaign-hack>.
- Passantino, J., & Reilly, L. (2024, August 14). *News outlets were sent leaked Trump campaign files. They chose not to publish them*. CNN. <https://edition.cnn.com/2024/08/13/media/trump-campaign-hack-news-media-report-iran-wikileaks/index.html>.
- Lyngaas, S., Perez, E., Cohen, Z., & Rabinowitz, H. (2024, September 12) *U.S. expected to charge Iranian hackers who targeted Trump campaign*. CNN. <https://edition.cnn.com/2024/09/12/politics/charges-expected-hackers-trump-campaign/index.html>.

- Robertson, N. (2024, July 18). *Iranian proxies attack U.S. base in Iraq for the first time in months*. Military Times. <https://www.militarytimes.com/news/your-military/2024/07/18/iranian-proxies-attack-us-base-in-iraq-for-the-first-time-in-months/>.
- Steven Lee Myers, Hsu, T., & Farnaz Fassihi. (2024, September 4). *Iran Emerges as a Top Disinformation Threat in U.S. Presidential Race*. Nytimes.com; The New York Times. <https://www.nytimes.com/2024/09/04/business/media/iran-disinformation-us-presidential-race.html>.
- Office of Public Affairs. (2016, March 24). *Seven Iranians Working for Islamic Revolutionary Guard Corps-Affiliated Entities Charged for Conducting Coordinated Campaign of Cyber Attacks Against U.S. Financial Sector*. Wwww.justice.gov. <https://www.justice.gov/opa/pr/seven-iranians-working-islamic-revolutionary-guard-corps-affiliated-entities-charged>.
- Roth, E. (2024, April 24). *Feds charge Iranian nationals for cyberattacks against U.S. government*. The Verge. <https://www.theverge.com/2024/4/24/24139160/doj-iranian-nationals-cyberattack-charge>.
- Office of Public Affairs. (2018, March 23). *Nine Iranians Charged With Conducting Massive Cyber Theft Campaign on Behalf of the Islamic Revolutionary Guard Corps*. Justice.gov. <https://www.justice.gov/opa/pr/nine-iranians-charged-conducting-massive-cyber-theft-campaign-behalf-islamic-revolutionary>.
- Tisdall, S. (2024, January 13). The U.S. isn't the biggest power in the Middle East any more. Iran is. *The Observer*. <https://www.theguardian.com/commentisfree/2024/jan/13/iran-is-thwith-china-and-russia-behind-it-iran-is-the-big-kid-on-the-block>.
- Bamford, J. (2024, March 29). *The Nuclear Explosion That Makes U.S. Aid to Israel Illegal*. Wwww.thenation.com. <https://www.thenation.com/article/world/israel-nuclear-weapons/>.
- Community, U. S. I. (2023). Annual Threat Assessment of the U.S. Intelligence Community [Review of *Annual Threat Assessment of the U.S. Intelligence Community*]. In O. of the Director of National Intelligence (Ed.), *www.dni.gov* (pp. 17–18). <https://www.dni.gov/files/ODNI/documents/assessments/ATA-2023-Unclassified-Report.pdf>.
- Rasmussen, S. E., & Norman, L. (2024, June 30). How Iran Defied the U.S. to Become an International Power [Review of *How Iran Defied the U.S. to Become an International Power*]. *The Wall Street Journal*.

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<https://www.wsj.com/world/middle-east/iran-international-influence-defies-america-d2c0f698>.

Pollack, K. M. (2023, August 15). *Iran's Grand Strategy Has Fundamentally Shifted*. Foreign Policy. <https://foreignpolicy.com/2023/08/15/irans-grand-strategy-has-fundamentally-shifted/>.

Hoffman, J. (2024). *Israel Is a Strategic Liability for the United States*. Cato.org. <https://www.cato.org/commentary/israel-strategic-liability-united-states>.

Glucroft, W. N. (2024, April 3). *Gaza war tests bond between Israel and United States*. Dw.com; Deutsche Welle. <https://www.dw.com/en/gaza-war-tests-bond-between-israel-and-united-states/a-68728712>.

Dagres, H. (2024, June 19). *Masoud Pezeshkian is a possible game changer in the upcoming Iranian presidential election*. Atlantic Council. <https://www.atlanticcouncil.org/blogs/iransource/masoud-pezeshkian-reformist-game-changer-election-president/>.

Nada, G. (2024, July 9). *What You Need to Know About Iran's Election and New President*. United States Institute of Peace. <https://www.usip.org/publications/2024/07/what-you-need-know-about-irans-election-and-new-president>.

UK, T. W. (2024, July 20). *Iran: does Masoud Pezeshkian's election mark a turning point?* The Week. <https://theweek.com/politics/iran-masoud-pezeshkians>.

Can Pezeshkian fix Iran's relations with the West? (2024). Europeanleadershipnetwork.org. <https://europeanleadershipnetwork.org/commentary/can-pezeshkian-fix-irans-relations-with-the-west/>.

Haleh Esfandiari on Iran's New Cabinet: A Mixed Bag. (2024, August 15). Wilson Center. <https://www.wilsoncenter.org/article/haleh-esfandiari-irans-new-cabinet-mixed-bag>.

Iran's President proposes an ex-nuclear negotiator as foreign minister. A woman is also on the list. (2024, August 11). AP News. <https://apnews.com/article/iran-former-nuclear-negotiator-new-foreign-minister-0e8b340f62bef6870476c7d4ac49d336>.

Palmer, E., & Seyed Bathaei. (2024, July 9). *What Iran's moderate new President Masoud Pezeshkian might try to change — and what he definitely won't*. Cbsnews.com; CBS News. <https://www.cbsnews.com/news/iran-new-president-masoud-pezeshkian-what-could-he-change/>.

- Tabaar, M. A. (2024, July 16). *Why Iran's New President Won't Change His Country*. Foreign Affairs. <https://www.foreignaffairs.com/middle-east/why-irans-new-president-wont-change-his-country#>.
- Goodman, M. (2024, February 7). *Deal With Iran Politically and Diplomatically, Not Militarily*. CounterPunch.org; CounterPunch. <https://www.counterpunch.org/2024/02/07/deal-with-iran-politically-and-diplomatically-not-militarily/>.
- Why Washington Has Struggled to Find the Right Policy Formula for Iran*. (2024). Carnegie Endowment for International Peace. <https://carnegieendowment.org/posts/2024/03/why-washington-has-struggled-to-find-the-right-policy-formula-for-iran?lang=en>.
- Esfandiary, D. (2020, February 11). *A Practical Policy to Re-Engage and Contain Iran*. The Century Foundation. <https://tcf.org/content/report/practical-policy-re-engage-contain-iran/>.
- Gordon, P. H. (2025, February 19). *America Has a Historic Opportunity in the Middle East*. Foreign Affairs. <https://www.foreignaffairs.com/united-states/america-has-historic-opportunity-middle-east#>.
- Thomas, C. (2024). *Iran: Background and U.S. Policy* (p. 20) [Review of *Iran: Background and U.S. Policy*]. U.S. Library of Congress. <https://crsreports.congress.gov/product/pdf/R/R47321>.
- Azodi, S. (2023, June 28). *Iran's nuclear program has a long history of advances, setbacks and diplomatic pauses* • Stimson Center. Stimson Center. <https://www.stimson.org/2023/irans-nuclear-program-has-a-long-history-of-advances-setbacks-and-diplomatic-pauses/>.
- English, A. A. (2024, July 6). *Iran's new President could ease, but won't end, nuclear tensions: Analysts*. Al Arabiya English. <https://english.alarabiya.net/News/middle-east/2024/07/06/iran-vote-winner-could-ease-but-will-not-end-nuclear-tensions-analysts>.
- Prioritizing Nuclear Negotiations With Iran*. (2025). Carnegie Endowment for International Peace. <https://carnegieendowment.org/posts/2025/02/iran-trump-nuclear-deal?lang=en>.
- Castillo, J., Schuessler, J., & Priebe, M. (2024, December 28). *Here's why Trump's foreign policy is hard to pin down*. MSNBC.com; MSNBC. <https://www.msnbc.com/opinion/msnbc-opinion/trump-foreign-policy-isolationist-realist-rcna183877>.
- How emotional reactions shape foreign policy decision-making*. (2024, October 21). Good Authority. <https://goodauthority.org/news/emotions-in-foreign-policy-leaders-trump-anger-emotional/>.

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Trump Ramps Up Pressure on Iran | Arms Control Association. (2015). Armscontrol.org. <https://www.armscontrol.org/blog/2025-02-13/trump-ramps-pressure-iran>.

Trump's Failing Iran Policy | Arms Control Association. (2019). Armscontrol.org. <https://www.armscontrol.org/act/2019-06/focus/trumps-failing-iran-policy>.

SARISOHN, H. (2025). *Donald Trump's inner circle: Marco Rubio, Elon Musk, and the rest*. the Jerusalem Post | JPost.com ; The Jerusalem Post. <https://www.jpost.com/american-politics/article-837770>.

Byman, D., & Trauger, K. (2024). Can Iran's New President Change the Regime's Confrontational Foreign Policy? *Www.csis.org*. <https://www.csis.org/analysis/can-irans-new-president-change-regimes-confrontational-foreign-policy>.

Iran's Eastward Turn to Russia and China. (n.d.). Www.brandeis.edu. Retrieved July 18, 2024, from <https://www.brandeis.edu/crown/publications/crown-conversations/cc-22.html>.

Why the U.S. and Iran hate each other. (2022, May 2). Responsible Statecraft. <https://responsiblestatecraft.org/2022/05/02/why-the-us-and-iran-hate-each-other/>.